

KOMPYUTER-TEXNIK EKSPERTIZASINI O'TKAZISHDA TEXNIK VA DASTURIY VOSITALARDAN FOYDALANISH

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Annotatsiya

Mazkur maqolada kompyuter-texnik ekspertizani o'tkazishda qo'llaniladigan texnik va dasturiy vositalarning o'рни hamda ularning amaliy imkoniyatlari yoritilgan. Raqamli dalillarni qidirish, nusxalash, tiklash va tahlil qilishda zamonaviy texnologiyalarning ahamiyati ilmiy asosda izohlanadi. Ekspertiza jarayonining bosqichlari, prinsiplari va forensika yo'nalishlarida qo'llaniladigan vositalar — disk, mobil, tarmoq va zararli dastur tahlil tizimlari izchil tahlil qilinadi. Natijada kompyuter-texnik ekspertiza samaradorligini oshiruvchi metod va vositalarning kompleks ta'siri ochib beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: kompyuter-texnik ekspertiza, raqamli dalil, forensika, texnik vositalar, dasturiy vositalar, ma'lumot tiklash, mobil forensika, tarmoq tahlili, zararli dasturlar.

Аннотация

В статье рассмотрена роль технических и программных средств, применяемых при проведении компьютерно-технической экспертизы, а также их практические возможности. Научно обосновано значение современных технологий при поиске, копировании, восстановлении и анализе цифровых доказательств. Подробно описаны этапы экспертизы, ее принципы, а также инструменты, используемые в дисковой, мобильной, сетевой и вредоносной форензике. Показано, как комплексное использование современных средств повышает эффективность компьютерно-технических исследований.

Ключевые слова: компьютерно-техническая экспертиза, цифровые доказательства, форензика, технические средства, программные средства, восстановление данных, мобильная форензика, сетевой анализ, вредоносное ПО.

Abstract

This article analyzes the role and practical capabilities of technical and software tools used in computer-technical forensics. It scientifically explains the significance of modern technologies in searching, copying, recovering, and analyzing digital evidence. The study discusses the stages and principles of forensic examination and provides an analytical overview of tools used in disk,

mobile, network, and malware forensics. The research highlights how the integrated use of these tools improves the effectiveness of computer-technical examinations.

Keywords: computer-technical forensics, digital evidence, forensic tools, technical tools, software tools, data recovery, mobile forensics, network analysis, malware analysis.

In the context of the rapid development of digital technologies, computer technical examination plays an important role in law enforcement, information security, combating fraud and cybercrime. The use of technical and software tools in the process of this examination allows you to identify cases, confirm facts, restore evidence and conduct reliable analysis. Therefore, studying the use of modern tools in this area is of great importance.

Computer technical examination is a special type of research aimed at studying, analyzing information contained in electronic devices, information carriers, computer systems and software, and determining facts. It performs the following tasks:

1. searching and collecting digital evidence;
2. recovering data;
3. determining the sequence of actions committed in computer systems;
4. analyzing malicious programs;
5. identifying traces in personal data and systems;
6. studying network traffic and logs.

Computer forensics cannot be carried out effectively without technical equipment. The following technical equipment is most often used:

1. Data carrier copying devices (Write Blocker)

They allow you to copy electronic devices in read-only mode without changing them. This ensures the integrity of evidence.

2. Professional servers and workstations

High-performance computers are needed to analyze large volumes of data, recover files, and perform cryptographic operations.

3. Mobile device inspection equipment

Dongles, scanners, and modules designed for mobile forensics (such as UFED, XRY) are used to extract information from smartphones and tablets.

4. Network monitoring devices

Special sniffer equipment is used to record traffic and analyze packets.

Software tools play a key role in identifying digital traces. The most important of them are:

1. Disk analysis and data recovery programs

EnCase

FTK (Forensic Toolkit)

Magnet AXIOM

They allow you to scan file systems, detect hidden files, and recover deleted data.

2. Mobile forensic programs

UFED Cellebrite

XRY

MOBILedit

These programs recover contacts, SMS, media files, geolocation, and application data.

3. Network forensic tools

Wireshark

Network Miner

TCPdump

They record network traffic and analyze packet sequences.

4. Malware analysis tools

IDA Pro

OllyDbg

Ghidra

These tools are used to decompile malware code, study its behavior, and determine the level of risk.

5. Password recovery and encryption analysis tools

Passware Kit

Hashcat

John the Ripper

Used to study encrypted files and password-protected systems.

Principles of using technical and software tools

The following principles are strictly followed during the examination process:

Integrity of evidence: write-blockers are used to prevent changes.

Reproducibility: the results must be the same during repeated examination.

Consistency: all stages are recorded in a log.

Legality: all actions must comply with procedural standards.

Security: data is stored encrypted.

Stages of computer technical examination

Preparatory stage

Search, seizure, collection of evidence, removal of devices, transportation.

Copying evidence

Obtaining physical and logical images, confirmation by hashing.

Analysis stage

Study of file structure, recovery of deleted data, analysis of logs, identification of malicious codes.

Evaluation of results

Comparison of the obtained data with each other, restoration of the mechanism of the event.

Preparation of conclusion

Formulation and presentation of the expert opinion.

Conclusion

Conducting computer forensics based on modern technical and software tools ensures the reliability and authenticity of digital evidence. It is of great importance in solving crimes, strengthening cybersecurity, and detecting fraud and illegal access to information. As technology develops, the skills of experts, the capabilities of tools, and the improvement of methods further increase the effectiveness of this field.

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